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NOTE

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The Coinage of the Kamoenoi. Part 2

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Fig. 1. Bronze coin of the Kamoenoi.
Classical Numismatic Group 123 (2023) 107. (2x)

In 2021 I discussed the two types of coinage then known to me of the Kamoenoi in Asia Minor. To publish is, of course, to create a hostage to fortune, and no sooner had I gathered the evidence than a new type emerged in commerce in the Classical Numismatic Group's sale 123 (Fig. 1). The three types may be summarised thus:²

Type 1

Obv. Bust of Artemis r., with bow and quiver at shoulder.

Rev. Eagle with wings open standing r. on thunderbolt; above, HΝΣ; below, ΔΕ; to l. and r., KAMO–HΝΩΝ

Type 2

Obv. Laureate head of Zeus right.

Rev. KAMO|HNON |ΔΕ| HΝΣ; all within oak wreath.

Type 3

Obv. Laureate head of Apollo right.

Rev. Stag grazing left; above and below, KAMOH|NON HN[Σ]; below stag, ΔΕ

Fig. 1. 4.17g 330° 19mm CNG 123 (2023) 107.

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² For the individual specimens of Types 1 and 2 see Meadows 2021.

Type	Specimens	Mean weight	Axis	Mean diameter
1	2	8.57	12	24.5
2	7	6.17	11-12	22.8
3	1	4.17	11	19

Table 1. Summary of physical properties.

From the shared monogram and, most probably, date, it is clear that the new type belongs with the other two as part of the same coinage. From Table 1 it appears that in our new type we are looking at a new denomination, now the smallest of the coinage.

What, if anything, can this new type add to our understanding of the Kamoenoi and their coinage? The obverse adds another anodyne depiction of a Greek deity: we now have Zeus, Artemis and Apollo. The quality of the engraving is again good, and simply reinforces the impression of a small community that approached competent engravers for some standard designs. The reverse of the grazing stag is, like the other two types, clearly borrowed. While the first two types suggested a Phrygian or east Lydian iconographic milieu, the new type plunges us into a broader pool. The earliest version of this type occurs at the mint of Ephesus on bronzes with bee in a wreath on the obverse, struck during the first half of the second century BC. The type reappeared at the mint in the later 2nd century, down into the 1st century on bronzes with a bust of Artemis on the obverse. But the popularity of the grazing stag reverse seems to have spread significantly in the 1st century BC as a result of the use of the type during the First Mithridatic War by Mithridates first on Pontic gold in 92 BC, on gold staters struck from 87–85 BC and silver tetradrachms struck from 86–85 at Pergamum, and subsequently on tetradrachms at his main Pontic silver mint from 88/7 BC.³ Furthermore, Philip Kinns has suggested that the adoption of the type by Magnesia on the Maeander for a remarkable silver coinage on the cistophoric standard also came during this conflict.⁴

While it seems highly unlikely that the coinage of the Kamoenoi can be dated to the same period as these prototypes, nor that it can be interpreted as a pro-Pontic statement as late as 55 BC, it seems more plausible that the general popularisation of the type, together with its continued popularity at Ephesus may lie behind its choice.

Bibliography

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 Kinns, P., 2006. 'A new didrachm of Magnesia on the Maeander', *NC* 166, pp. 41–7.
 Meadows, A.R., 2021. 'The land that time forgot: the coinage of the Kamoenoi', *NC* 181, pp. 93–102.

³ For the Mithridatic coinage see Callatay (1997), pp. 4-5 and 23 (Pergamum), pp. 16-22 (Pontic).

⁴ Kinns (2006), especially pp. 46-7.